

Probability Derivative of Entropy as Information?

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Entropy in the Maxwell-Boltzmann example of a gas with no potential may be mapped into a set of trial runs for a single gas particle with probabilities $p(e_i)$. If N , the number of trials, approaches infinite, the probability of a set of runs is $\text{Product over } i \exp\{\ln(p(e_i)) N p(e_i)h\}$. This is the same for any set of N runs and so probability is $1/\text{permutations of } N \text{ particles with } n(e_i)$. If $\ln\{\text{number of permutations is maximized}\}$ (i.e. probability minimized) subject to a constraint, say $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$, then one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. The \ln of the number of permutations is proportional to a function called entropy which is associated with a maximization of permutations. We argue, however, that there are two unusual issues with the above approach. First, there is no need to take \ln of the number of arrangements when maximizing. This is specifically done to convert a sum into a product, emphasizing the independence of the trial runs which we argue is an important feature. The second is the constraint. We argue that a very specific constraint is needed, namely one containing the information relevant to physical collision which creates the equilibrium. We have argued this in previous notes.

The point we wish to make here is that $d/d n(e_i)$ Entropy density = $-e_i/T$ = information. Thus entropy density is a function whose derivative with respect to $n(e_i)$ yields the information of the system. This is not unlike the quantum free particle case for which $-id/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p$ = information. Mathematically $d/dn(e_i)$ is supposed to represent a change in the function $n(e_i)$, but n is simply a variable and one may argue that $d/dn(e_i)$ means $\text{function}(n(e_i)+1) - \text{function}(n(e_i))$. Thus one has a function which when changed by adding one particle minus its original value yields the information of the particle. Given that one considers a particle to be independent, then the argument of \ln should display this independence. $n \ln(n) = \ln(n^{\text{power } n})$ has this property. If $n \rightarrow n+1$, n or $n+1$ in the base is essentially the same, but there is an extra $n+1$ due to the exponent. \ln then pulls this out so the extra particle carries an information of $-e_i/T$.

We argue that the idea of entropy is linked to a more physical idea of reaction balance which in turn focuses on conservation of energy and probability. If energy e_i multiplied by a constant carries the same information as $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ converted by a function into a sum of probabilities (i.e. using \ln), one has an expression linking the information content of $p(e_i)$ to $-e_i/T$, the information of the particle. This expression may be integrated by $p(e_i)$ (treating e_i as a constant) to obtain the entropy on one side and $-e_i/T p(e_i)$ on the other, i.e. the special constraint. Thus instead of thinking of maximizing arrangements etc, we suggest that one consider probability and information associated with a collision which creates the equilibrium and focus on the independence of the particle which moves from one collision to another.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

If one considers a gas of N particles (where N is very large) and a total energy E_{total} , it is tempting to consider all possible distributions of $n(e_i)$ such that $\text{Sum over } n(e_i) = N$ and $\text{Sum over } e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$. Given that one does not know the weights of these distributions, it is assumed that each has the same weight.

An alternative approach to analysing the gas is to consider a single particle which undergoes N collisions. For N very large, e_i should appear $N p(e_i)$ times. Relaxing the strict constraint E_{total} and replacing it with $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{total}$ allows one to consider each particle in a two body collision as independent from the surrounding particles (which have a certain energy at the time of the collision and so in principle limit the total energy which the colliding pair may have). In such a case, the probability of a set of N trial runs is:

$$P1 = \text{Probability of a specific set of } N \text{ trial runs} = \text{Product over } i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)} \quad ((1))$$

For N very large, the probability of any set of N trial runs is the same, so:

$$P1 = 1 / \{\text{permutations of } N \text{ particles with } n(e_i) = N p(e_i)\} \quad ((2))$$

The general approach is to minimize $P1$ by maximizing the permutations (or \ln of them to convert the product into a sum) subject to a constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. We argue that \ln is a specific function which converts a product of probabilities into a sum because $e_i n(e_i)$ is in the form of a sum. Furthermore, e_i is not an arbitrary choice of constraint, but is exactly the information of a particle involved in a collision which creates the equilibrium. We argue that the idea of maximizing permutations (e.g. disorder etc) subject to a constraint) and using \ln for convenience is really linked to different ideas, although in the MB example, the permutations are a physical reality. They need not, however, be considered to be the number of arrangements (in one dimension it seems) of the gas particles. Rather it is the number of arrangements of collision results of a single particle. If thought of in this way, it seems that one should analyse a two body collision.

Two Body Collisions i.e. Reaction Balance

Two body collisions physically create the equilibrium in a gas and identify the value of information uniquely. It is this information which appears in the constraint in the maximization of entropy approach. If the particle is considered to be colliding independently, which is the picture in the above section, it carries with it the physical information e_i for each collision, but there is also a single particle probability $p(e_i)$. This probability must be multiplied by $p(e_j)$ in a collision between e_i and e_j and so it is the joint (AND) probability which is conserved. $p(e_i)$ only brings part of this probability yet it contributes e_i . One needs to find an expression which breaks the probability into a sum i.e.

$$\ln(p(e_i)p(e_j)) = \ln(p(e_i)) + \ln(p(e_j)) \quad ((3))$$

This way e_i multiplied by a constant $-e_i/T$, i.e. the physical information, is considered to be identical to $\ln(p(e_i))$ which is also carried along from one collision to another. Using $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$:

$$\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((4)) \text{ which yields the MB distribution with } N \text{ already assumed to be very large}$$

((4)) may be integrated over $dn(e_i)$ to yield essentially:

$$n(e_i)\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad n(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

On the RHS of ((4)) one adds $n(e_i)$ particles each with $-e_i/T$. On the LHS side, however, one deals with probabilities. The expression $n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ is the Stirling approximation form of $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ which in turn is \ln of the number of permutations of $n(e_i)$ particles. Thus even though each particle has an information of $-e_i/T$, which is equal to $\ln(n(e_i))$, the latter is not a constant during integration. One need not think in terms of factorials, however, but rather in terms of:

$$n(e_i)\ln(n(e_i)) = \ln \{ n(e_i)^{n(e_i)} \} \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is the form of a probability to the power of the number of times it occurs, but ensures independence of a particle moving from one collision to another. Taking the derivative $d/dn(e_i)$ of $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ is like considering $\ln([n(e_i)+1]!) - \ln(n(e_i)!)$ which yields the information of a single particle i.e. $-e_i/T$. The same result follows using ((6)) One may note that $\ln(n(e_i)+1)$ is similar to the sum form of the probability carried by $p(e_i)$ i.e. $\ln(p(e_i)p(e_j)) = \ln(p(e_i)) + \ln(p(e_j))$. \ln is used to make a single particle independent as it moves from one collision to another given the argument of ((6)) and so this value $\ln(n(e_i)+1)$ is simply the information $-e_i/T$. Thus it is not really the fact that one takes a derivative $d/dn(e_i)$ of a $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ which is important, but rather that adding an extra particle only brings in the information (in sum form) of this extra particle, namely $-e_i/T$ i.e.

$$\ln([n(e_i)+1]!) = \ln(n(e_i)+1) + \ln(n(e_i)!) \quad ((7))$$

{A key point in adding an extra particle to the argument of \ln is that this particle must appear as independent. One must have a kind of independence already built into the argument of \ln . This independence is achieved by having a product of factors i.e. ((6)) so that $n(e_i) \rightarrow n(e_i)+1$ in the exponent yields an extra factor while $n(e_i)+1$ in the base is approximately the same because $n(e_i)$ is considered to be very large. Thus one does not need to actually think in terms of factorials in the high N limit. }

In other words, maximizing degeneracy or permutations (which formally occurs) does not seem to be the main physical idea.

The important issue is that $d/dn(e_i)$ Entropy density returns the information of a single $n(e_i)$ particle namely $-e_i/T$. This in turn follows from the nature of the collision. As a result, it may not be particularly important to consider permutations of $n(e_i)$ particles as particularly relevant. In fact, the reaction balance approach does not require any such notion and no maximization of any function.

Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac Approaches

To see the above ideas more clearly, one may consider the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac situations. As argued above, it is the collisions i.e. energy conservation and

probability conservation which are important. Physically there is more information contained in the reaction of fermions or bosons than in the MB case. For a fermion scattering into a state, there is a reduction in probability if the state is occupied. On average this is $1-n(e_i)$. For bosons, there is an enhancement of $1+n(e_i)$. The energy is conserved i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, but probability conservation is:

$$n(e_1)[1-/+ n(e_3)] n(e_2) [1-/+ n(e_4)] = n(e_3)[1-/+n(e_1)] n(e_4)[1-/+n(e_2)] \quad ((8))$$

where - represents fermions and + bosons.

Probability conservation is no longer as simple as $p(e_i)p(e_j)$. One needs again, however, a function which may be associated with a single particle moving from one collision to another. It would be ideal to have this particle independent and ((8)) allows this if one collects terms with the same energies. Thus:

$$\text{Ln}\{ n(e_i) / [1-/+ n(e_i)] \} = -e_i/T \quad ((9))$$

The LHS side of ((9)) is the new quantity which represents the information $-e_i/T$ associated with each collision. Formally one may integrate over $dn(e_i)$ and associate the result with an equivalent factorial expression using Stirling's approximation, but $d/d n(e_i)$ again brings back the result of adding one more particle which is considered to be independent and so this only contributes an information of $-e_i/T$.

One might think of the argument in {} in the LHS of ((9)) as a modified particle number and try to use factorial arguments. The form ((6)), however, shows that the integral of ((9)) with respect to $dn(e_i)$ is in the form of a sum of terms $(a+bn(e_i)) \ln(a+bn(e_i))$. These may be thought of as $\ln(f)$ which again leads to the addition of a single particle i.e. $d/dn(e_i)$ minus the original result as overall yielding the information of the single particle namely the physical value $-e_i/T$ related to the collision. Thus we argue that one does not necessarily need to think in terms of factorials and permutations. In the high n limit one may consider $n! = n \ln(n)$ with the latter being $\ln(n^n)$. This last term does not necessarily need to be thought of in terms of factorials and hence degeneracies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint is often seen as maximizing permutations or arrangements subject to a subjective constraint. We argue that reaction balance fixes the physical variable which represents information in a two body collision, i.e. e_i , which is the variable which must appear in the constraint. Furthermore, one has conservation of probability, but this occurs at the level of two particles, not one, so one has $p(e_i)p(e_j)$ in the MB case. This needs to be converted into a single particle form using the function \ln . $\ln(p(e_i))$ may be considered equivalent to $-e_i/T$ if one assumes both carry the same information.

If one wishes to consider a function, i.e. entropy density, such that $d/dn(e_i)$ entropy density = $-e_i/T$ = information where $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } -e_i/T n(e_i)$ is the constraint, one may

note that an independent particle moves from one collision to another bringing information $-e_i/T$ to each collision. $d/dn(e_i)$ means $n(e_i) \rightarrow n(e_i)+1$. One may ask: What function of \ln would allow for such an independence? The answer is: $\ln(n(e_i)^{n(e_i)})$ because $n(e_i)$ and $n(e_i)+1$ are essentially identical, but the power brings in an extra $n(e_i)$ and so one has $\ln(n(e_i)+1)$ plus the original value which is removed through the derivative. This function is exactly $n(e_i)\ln(n(e_i))$ which follows in the MB case from integrating $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ over $dn(e_i)$.

Thus one does not really need to think in terms of factorials and arrangements even if one considers an entropy function. It is true, however, that in Stirling's approximation $n\ln(n) \approx \ln(n!)$ so one may think in terms of factorials in a clear way in the MB case, but matters become a little more complicated in the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac cases, and we argue one may not again need to think in terms of factorials, but rather in terms of $n(e_i) \rightarrow n(e_i)+1$ leading to an increase in information of $-e_i/T$ with $\ln(\text{appropriate function})$ on the LHS. This appropriate function follows from reaction balance i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and a probability conservation equation which physically describes two body scattering. One may group all terms with e_i (which is possible in the BE and FD cases, but probably not in all physical cases) and then apply \ln . We argue that one may think of an entropy density function such that $d/dn(e_i)$ yields $-e_i/T$, but does not necessarily need to associate this with factorials. One may instead consider the result to be of the form $\ln((a+bn)^{a+bn})$ such that $n \rightarrow n+1$ yields an extra factor which appears as $\ln(a+bn)$ indicating the independence of a single particle which moves from one collision to another.